

SUPSI

SUPSI: Final report CHEERS Cultural HEritage. Risks and Securing activities

I. Information related to the project

Name of the project	CHEERS Cultural HEritage. Risks and Securing activities
Institution responsible for the project	University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI) - Department for Environment Constructions and Design - Institute of Design (previously known as Laboratory of visual culture) in collaboration with the Institute of Earth Sciences
Related INTERREG Program	Alpine Space
Cantons and municipalities involved	Canton Ticino With the endorsement of the Canton Ticino DECS Dipartimento dell'educazione, della cultura e dello sport / Department of education, culture and sport of Canton https://www4.ti.ch/decs/dipartimento/
Duration of the project	17 April 2018 - 31 August 2021
Project team	Iolanda Pensa, Institute of Design (principal investigator) Marta Pucciarelli, Institute of Design Christian Ambrosi, Institute of Earth Sciences Cristian Scapozza, Institute of Earth Sciences Dorota Czerski, Institute of Earth Sciences
Open Access documentation	SUPSI documentation about the project on Open Science Framework (OSF)

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II. Objectives and progress

Summary of the project

The Alps are home to an outstanding material and immaterial cultural heritage that characterizes their identity and strongly contributes to their local economies. Natural hazards, affecting the Alpine territory and expected to grow worse in future climate scenarios, represent a major threat to cultural heritage, jeopardizing it, up to the complete loss of both movable and immovable assets. In the last decades, hazards and risks management became a priority action field in the Alpine countries, setting prevention and emergency measures effective in protecting human lives.

For the Canton Ticino, heritage represents a fundamental asset for its touristic economy. Potentiating the capacity of risk management and intervention in case of natural events is essential to the safeguarding of jobs and the competitiveness of the territory.

The project aimed at valorizing cultural heritage by (A) promoting new national and transnational governance and intervention schemes involving the main actors at different levels working on the management and protection of cultural heritage and (B) innovating approaches and tools to secure cultural assets affected by natural hazards. These goals have been achieved through a four steps process: 1) building the knowledge base for identifying and valorizing the cultural heritage stock at risk; 2) defining reference conservation/securing approaches, techniques and training for Civil Protection Operators; 3) developing new models of emergency planning to protect cultural heritage, built on shared pilot experience and transferable at transnational level; 4) looking ahead, identifying direct impacts and degradation processes driven by climate change and capitalizing innovation technologies for effective for more effective comprehensive adaptation policies.

Project progress

The Department for Environment Constructions and Design at University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI) participated and contributed to the transborder project CHEERS with an applied approach focussed on the territory of Canton Ticino. The contribution of SUPSI was based on the specific expertise of the Institute of Design (previously known as Laboratory of visual culture) in communication projects relying on open data and online collaborative projects, and on the specific expertise of the Institute of Earth Sciences in geological and hydrological risk management.

As planned within the CHEERS project, SUPSI potentiated the results of previous projects related to natural risks and cultural heritage in cooperation with the Alpine partners with a focus on evaluating value, costs and efficiency of risk prevention applied to our local heritage, by fostering the use of open maps and active citizenship in monitoring the territory and by evaluating the use of drones and fostering training for local operators.

More specifically, the Institute of Design and the Institute of Earth Sciences contributed in the discussions and the definition of the state of the art on the impacts that tangible cultural heritage is expected to undergo also due to climate change scenarios, and of the state of the art on innovative experiences using, in the framework of Alpine territories, Information and Communication Technologies to safeguard cultural heritages and communicate risks and emergency plans to citizens.

The Institute of Design contributed with an evaluation related to the use of open data and open maps for risk preventions and management, and it contributed to the communication with its expertise in open data, open content and on collaborative online projects such as OpenStreetMap, Wikimedia Commons, Wikidata and the initiative Wiki Loves Monuments involving contributors to Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons. The use of OpenStreetMap is strategic to involve citizens, to merge data from different sources and to produce dataset open for reuse, modification and commercial purposes. The use of this tool for emergencies is already well documented and its use is growing among civil protection and other organisations involved in managing territories and calamities.

Beyond the project planned activities, to assure a significant impact of the project in Canton Ticino, SUPSI contributed to all the project activities with a focus on Switzerland. Furthermore it documented and analyzed the Civil Protection specialized training by attending it and by collected information about their procedures and approach; we documented and analyzed two civil protection exercises for the recovery of cultural assets in the church Madonna del Rosario in Bironico and the church San Martino in Olivone. We organized the "Transnational Conference Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection" (Castelgrande Bellinzona, 21 February 2020) in collaboration with the Department of education, culture and sport of Canton Ticino. We

produced a collaborative emergency plan for the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio (Museo storico etnografico Valle di Blenio) and we presented the methodology to the association of the ethnographical museums of Canton Ticino (AMET).

Correlation with the NRP Nuova Politica Regionale

The CHEERS project supported better management of resources with a focus on improving the protection of cultural heritage against natural hazards. It contributed to the implementation of Strategy no. 2 of the Swiss territorial project "Enhancing settlements and landscapes", which provides in particular for the protection of cultural heritage. This project also contributed to the Principles for the Protection of Historic Monuments in Switzerland, by the Federal Commission of Historic Monuments (CFMS). The applicative nature of the project, through a pilot study in Canton Ticino, developed and made operational new approaches, techniques and training tools for the conservation and protection of cultural heritage of national interest at risk, directing attention and involvement of the national commission on this topic, and proposing replicable and scalable results throughout the Swiss territory.

More specifically the project contributed to observe the current emergency plans for cultural heritage in Canton Ticino and to produce a collaborative emergency plan for the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio.

III. Follow up of the project

The topics of heritage protection and of cultural open data are at the centre of the CHEERS project and continue to be developed by SUPSI within its institutes and departments. Cultural open data and maps are at the centre of new projects implemented by the Institute of Design. Currently we are implementing the follow up of the project by:

- Training museum curators about preservation and open data. The CHEERS project was essential to trigger and facilitate contacts with the regional museums and their digital strategy. The projects and in particular the international conference about Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection organized in Bellinzona in February 2021 was important to consolidate the relationships with the Canton in this area, with the city of Lugano and with cultural and territorial institutions.
- Implementing as lead organization a national project about Open Science for arts design music involving all art and design schools in Switzerland (2022-2024)
- Organizing as lead organization the Swiss GLAMHack in collaboration with OpenGLAM Switzerland (3-5 November 2022). The event is a hackathon aiming at developing new projects products and services based on open data of cultural institutions and research.
- Planning a research project with the Canton related to open data in Ticino and about a shared transborder cultural agenda based on Open Data.

The Department for Environment Constructions and Design at SUPSI has established in 2021 an interdisciplinary group focusing on heritage; all SUPSI members of the project CHEERS are part of this thematic interdisciplinary group.

The relationships with the international partner organisations involved in the CHEERS project are very positive and we have already been invited to join a new proposal by one of the Italian partners.

Project plan, completed activities and variations

WP	Expected contribution to the project	Variations
WP M Management (04.2018 - 08.2021)	<p>General management of the project</p> <p>√ Participation in meetings with project partners and with the Project Management Board. 21-22 June 2018 in Seveso - kick-off meeting (Iolanda Pensa); 21-22 June 2018 in Milan (Iolanda Pensa, Cristian Scapozza, Christian Ambrosi); 6-8 May 2019 in Idrija in Slovenia (Marta Pucciarelli); Internal coordination meeting - pre-PSG meeting related WPT3 (Marta Pucciarelli, 15 May 2020); Project Steering Group web conference meeting (Marta Pucciarelli, 20 May 2020), Internal coordination meeting online meeting 29-30 June 2020 (Iolanda Pensa and Marta Pucciarelli); Meeting bilateral WP4 (Marta Pucciarelli, 3 November 2020), 2 February 2021 (Marta Pucciarelli and Iolanda Pensa), sourcebook 4 June 2021 (Iolanda Pensa), 14 July 2021 bilateral meeting.</p> <p>√ Preparation of activity reports for the Alpine Space Program and the ARE.</p>	<p>+SUPSI contributed actively to the project by organizing and hosting meetings and by contributing to the workpackages more than planned.</p> <p>+Support in using open licenses within the project and among partners and implementation of Open Science</p> <p>+Participation in the technical committee established to produce the CHEERS guidelines</p>
WP T1 Alpine Cultural Heritage: value and vulnerability (04.2018 - 06.2019)	<p>The Institute of Design at SUPSI contributes with an evaluation of the use of open data and open maps for risk preventions and management. The use of OpenStreetMap is strategic to involve citizens, to merge data from different sources and to produce dataset open for reuse, modification and commercial purposes. The use of this tool for emergencies is already well documented and its use is growing among civil protection and other organisations involved in managing territories and calamities.</p> <p>√ Evaluation of the use of open data and maps for risk prevention and management.</p> <p>More specifically:</p> <p>√ Presentation of the project to Wikimedia and OpenStreetMap communities.</p> <p>√ Preparatory work literature review of guidelines, documents, policies and international good practices.</p> <p>√ Text about Open Data and Open Maps for heritage protection included in the sourcebook</p> <p>+Organisation of the international conference “Transnational Conference Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection”, 21 February 2020 in collaboration with the Department of education, culture and sport of Canton Ticino; report about the conference.</p>	<p>+ Overview about natural hazards in Switzerland.</p> <p>+Review and feedback on the document "Alpine cultural heritage and natural hazards: where do we stand?" (report D.T1.1.1) -</p> <p>+ State of the art of research about heritage and natural hazards in Switzerland.</p> <p>+ Participation in documenting the state of the art of research about heritage and natural hazards in Europe.</p> <p>+Conceptual toolkit for the identification of actual exposure of cultural assets to risk focusing on the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio (Museo storico etnografico Valle di Blenio).</p> <p>+Assessment method for assets evaluation and priority interventions with a focus on the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio.</p> <p>+Deliverable D.T1.2.2. Iolanda Pensa, Cristian Scapozza, & Marta Pucciarelli. (2020). Report on the application of the tool for assets evaluation in the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio and prioritization of interventions. Zenodo.</p>

WP	Expected contribution to the project	Variations
WP T2 Advancing Hazard & Exposure Assessment methodologies applied to the field of Cultural Heritage protection (09.2018 - 03.2021)	<p>√ Definition, in collaboration with civil protection operators, of the pilot area in the Canton of Ticino</p> <p>√ Analysis of the territory and mapping of areas at risk</p> <p>More specifically:</p> <p>√ Meeting with the civil protection of Ticino on 28 March 2019 (Iolanda Pensa and Cristian Scapozza).</p> <p>√ Preliminary selection of the Swiss case studies (Bellinzona, Campo Vallemaggia in Canton Ticino and Bondo in the Canton of Grisons). Documentation related to the case studies and updates to Wikipedia articles.</p> <p>√ Presentation of the case study about Bellinzona. Documentation about the case study</p>	<p>+ We participated in the Ticino Civil Protection specialized training for cultural heritage, Rivera, 13-17 My 2019 (Iolanda Pensa). Collecting information and feedback about their procedures and approach.</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T1.2.2. Iolanda Pensa, Cristian Scapozza, & Marta Pucciarelli. (2020). Report on the application of the tool for assets evaluation in the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio and prioritization of interventions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338977</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Marta Pucciarelli. (2022). Cultural heritage in Switzerland and Canton Ticino and their inventories. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338995. Deliverable Knowledge base on geo-spatial catalogues of cultural heritage in the Alpine area (country contribution) - Switzerland</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Marta Pucciarelli, Cristian Scapozza, & Iolanda Pensa. (2020). Civil protection in Switzerland and emergency planning instruments and cultural heritage safeguarding. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7339039. Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Critical overview of Emergency Planning schemes at Alpine level. Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue?</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T2.1.1 Knowledge base on natural hazard mapping in the Alpine area D.T2.1.1 - Focus on Switzerland (Cristian Scapozza and Dorota Czerski).</p>
WP T3 Alpine Cultural Heritage Protection : approaches and techniques (01.2019 - 04.2021)	<p>On the pilot area selected and with an applied approach, SUPSI discusses and tests the definition of procedures specifically oriented at cultural heritage.</p> <p>√ Discussion and experimentation of the definition of procedures specifically oriented to cultural heritage in the pilot area and with an applied and training approach.</p> <p>√ Documentation and analysis about the exercise by the Civil Protection on the church Madonna del Rosario in Bironico, 17 May 2019 (Iolanda Pensa)</p> <p>√ Documentation and analysis about the exercise by the Civil Protection on the church San Martino in Olivone (exercise organized by the Civil Protection Tre Valli and the firemen of Blenio), 26 September 2019 (Marta Pucciarelli).</p>	<p>We used as case study two exercises organized by the civil protection in collaboration with the firemen. The Civil Protection of Ticino allowed us to participate in their training and exercises. This is coherent with the project because it allows us to observe the current training methodology for the protection of cultural heritage, to analyze the current situation by attending exercises and to review content and practices.</p> <p>+ Collaboration with the civil protection and with the public administration and feedback based on the experience of the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio</p> <p>+ T3.2. Education and training learning units on the Cultural Heritage and Risk management cycle related to the Ticino Civil Protection specialized training for cultural heritage; innovation concepts of civil protection plans for cultural heritage assets protection & schemes of simulation exercises — Presentation of the experience of the Civil Protection in Ticino</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Knowledge base on geo-spatial catalogues of cultural heritage in the Alpine area (country contribution)</p> <p>+ Deliverable D.T2.3.2 Marta Pucciarelli, & Iolanda Pensa. (2020). Report on the Transnational Conference Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection. Zenodo.</p>

WP	Expected contribution to the project	Variations
<p>WP T4 Emergency planning and salvaging (09.2019 - 05.2021)</p>	<p>SUPSI contributed in the discussion and definition of the state of the art on the impacts that tangible cultural heritages are expected to undergo due to climate change scenarios, and of the state of the art on innovative experiences using, in the framework of Alpine territories, Information and Communication Technologies to safeguard cultural heritages and communicate risks and Emergency Plans to citizens. Furthermore - always in the pilot area, SUPSI verifies the current procedure and activates the use of new tools suggested as outcomes of the state of the arts. New activities: preparatory meetings for the activity.</p> <p>√ Contribution to the discussion and definition of the state of the art on the impacts that tangible cultural heritages should undergo due to climate change scenarios. Deliverable D.T4.1.1 Critical overview of Emergency Planning schemes at Alpine level - New activities: - "Cultural HERitagE. Risks and Securing activities". Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue? Switzerland</p> <p>√ Contribution to the discussion and definition of the state of the art of innovative experiences using, within the Alpine territories, information and communication technologies to safeguard cultural heritage and communicate risks and emergency plans to citizens. √ Verification of the current procedure and activation of the use of new tools suggested as results of the state of the art.</p>	<p>+ To concretely contribute to the project and to actively support heritage protection in Canton Ticino, we focussed on producing the emergency plan of the historical and ethnographical Museum of the Valle di Blenio</p> <p>√ "Cultural HERitagE. Risks and Securing activities". Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue? Switzerland</p>
<p>WP C Communication (04.2018 - 08.2021)</p>	<p>SUPSI actively contributes to the communication of the project with the team of the Laboratory of visual culture (now Institute of design), specialized in communication strategies and design. More specifically SUPSI contributes to the communication with its expertise in open data, open content and on collaborative online projects such as OpenStreetMap, Wikimedia Commons, Wikidata and the initiative Wiki Loves Monuments involving contributors to Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons.</p> <p>√ Participation in the project activities related to communication</p> <p>More precisely: √ Contacts with the local stakeholders (Canton and civil protection). Contacts with colleagues at SUPSI working on the preservation and valorization of heritage. √ Series of articles on Wikipedia about the civil protection and Canton Ticino √ Networking and contacts with OpenStreetMaps and Wikimedia communities, Wikimedia Italia, Creative Commons international. √ T1. 2 Establishment of the CHEERS experts and stakeholders network for cultural heritage protection in the Alps --> focus on Canton Ticino √ Participation in the project conferences: Mid-term Conference (Marta Pucciarelli, 18 December 2020); 14 June 2021 Final Conference</p>	<p>+Planning and organization of the international conference "Transnational Conference Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection", 21 February 2020 in collaboration with the Department of education, culture and sport of Canton Ticino; report about the conference. +Reinforcement of the collaboration between SUSPI and ICCROM, with the active involvement of the Institute of Earth Sciences in the initiative Climate.Culture.Peace +Facilitating the collaboration with ICCROM for the e-sourcebook +The focus on an historical and ethnographic museum allowed us to involve the Association of ethnographic museums of Ticino (AMET), a very active association with members in the entire Canton Ticino territory and capable of disseminating good practices among its members. + Dissemination of Cheers' project results at the "Youth Forum: Intergenerational Dialogue on Climate.Culture.Peace" as part of Climate.Culture.Peace, an international virtual conference aimed at exploring the interconnections between culture, climate change, peace and disaster resilience.</p>

Documentation of the project

Link to the full documentation of the project produced by SUPSI on Open Science Framework <https://osf.io/xpt97/>

- Deliverable D.T1.2.2. Iolanda Pensa, Cristian Scapozza, & Marta Pucciarelli. (2020). Report on the application of the tool for assets evaluation in the Museo Valle di Blenio and prioritization of interventions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338977>
- Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Marta Pucciarelli. (2021). Cultural heritage in Switzerland and Canton Ticino and their inventories. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338995>. Deliverable Knowledge base on geo-spatial catalogues of cultural heritage in the Alpine area (country contribution) - Switzerland
- Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Marta Pucciarelli, Cristian Scapozza, & Iolanda Pensa. (2020). Civil protection in Switzerland and emergency planning instruments and cultural heritage safeguarding. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7339039>. Deliverable D.T2.2.1 Critical overview of Emergency Planning schemes at Alpine level. Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue?
- Deliverable D.T2.1.1 Knowledge base on natural hazard mapping in the Alpine area D.T2.1.1 - Focus on Switzerland (Cristian Scapozza and Dorota Czerski).
- Deliverable D.T2.3.2 Marta Pucciarelli, & Iolanda Pensa. (2020). Report on the Transnational Conference Open Data and Open Maps for Heritage Protection. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338941>
- Deliverable D.T4.1.1 Critical overview of Emergency Planning schemes at Alpine level - New activities: - "Cultural HEritagE. Risks and Securing activities". Activity A.T4.1 Emergency Planning and cultural heritages protection: how do the Alps deal with this issue? Switzerland
- Iolanda Pensa (2021), Open Data for Heritage Protection, e-Sourcebook.
- Marta Pucciarelli and Iolanda Pensa (2022). Open Data, Open Maps and Heritage Protection. Youth Forum: Intergenerational Dialogue on Climate.Culture.Peace, online virtual conference 24-28 January 2022.

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